

THICK POLYMER COMPOSITES MANUFACTURING

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ABSTRACT

Thick polymer composites are being promoted to be used in naval applications (submersibles, ship hulls) and in the automotive and aerospace industries. With interests in thick composite applications growing, there is a need to develop the manufacturing technology to support thick composite processing. The research issues which need to be addressed in thick composites manufacturing are discussed in terms of thermal effects and consolidational effects. Definitions of what is meant by a thick composite are given. Two processing methods recently developed for thick composites manufacturing called stage curing and continuous curing are reviewed.

1. Introduction

Historically, composite materials have been used in thin laminated structural applications. The manufacturing processes and equipment supporting these applications has been developed with this geometry in mind. Thick polymer composites are being promoted to be used in naval applications (submersibles, ship hulls) and in civil structures (bridges, columns, decking). With interests in thick composite applications growing, there is a need to develop the manufacturing technology to support thick composite processing.

Thick composite materials possess many unique challenges in manufacturing. Specifically, there are five problem areas: 1) thermal spiking [1-3], 2) non-uniform cure, 3) non-uniform consolidation [4-6], 4) lengthy process cycle times, 5) residual stresses [7-9]. The characteristic time scale for heat transfer into the interior of a thick composite part is lengthy due to the relatively poor transverse thermal conductivity of polymer matrix composites. This leads to extremely long process cycle times. In addition, the exothermic cure reaction releases energy in the interior of the part which raises the interior temperature to levels which can degrade the matrix. This behavior is referred to as thermal spiking. The uneven distribution of temperature across the thickness leads to non-uniform curing and consolidation. During processing the outer layers will cure and consolidate first. Subsequently, as thermal energy diffuses to the interior, the central region will begin to cure and consolidate. This non-uniformity in temperature history leads to a distribution in mechanical properties across the part thickness.

New research into thick thermosetting polymer matrix composites manufacturing has shown that these problems can be resolved while simultaneously reducing process cycle times. Two such methods are discussed in the paper; staged curing and continuous curing.

2. Technical Issues

The technical issues in thick composites processing can be grouped into two broad areas: thermal effects and consolidation effects.

2.1 Thermal Effects

Polymer composites are poor thermal conductors transverse to the fiber direction. Lengthy process cycle times are required to conduct thermal energy into the interior of the material. As the thickness is increased, longer times are required to elevate the temperature of the interior region. Once the temperature has risen above some minimum temperature for curing, energy is released from the exothermic crosslinking reaction. Depending on the strength of this exothermic reaction (heat of reaction) and how quickly it occurs (Arrhenius constants), too much energy may be released too quickly in the interior of the part. This leads to the problem of thermal spiking. In the extreme case, the interior temperature exceeds the degradation temperature of the polymer matrix. If this occurs, the matrix can be charred and the mechanical integrity of the material is severely sacrificed.

Materials which exhibit small exotherms may be fabricated to relatively thick dimensions without thermal spiking. Strongly exothermic materials, on the other hand, cannot be processed without thermal spiking to any appreciable thickness. There is a need to define what is meant by a thermally-thick polymer composite.

The work of Stevenson [10] presents a method to characterize what is meant by a thermally-thick part. The Damkohler number, Da , is a dimensionless parameter which is a measure of the rate of heat released during reaction to the rate of heat conduction.

$$Da = \frac{\gamma H_R}{C_p t_r} \cdot \frac{h^2}{\alpha (T_w - T_o)} \approx \frac{\left(\frac{dT}{dt}\right)_{reaction}}{\left(\frac{dT}{dt}\right)_{conduction}} \quad (1)$$

The rate of heat conduction depends upon the thermal diffusivity (α), the thickness (h), the wall temperature (T_w), and the initial temperature (T_o). The rate of reaction heating is dependent on the heat of reaction (H_R), and specific heat (C_p), the resin mass fraction (γ), and the characteristic reaction time (t_r). The ratio of these two quantities provides a framework for defining a thermally-thick material. For $Da > 1$ the reaction exotherm outpaces the ability of the material to conduct heat away and thermal spiking will result. When $Da < 1$ the material behaves like a "thin" part such that the exotherm energy is conducted away from the interior in a sufficiently rapid manner. This analysis assumes a one-dimensional mode of heat conduction. Doubly-contoured geometries and corners may necessitate analysis of the two- or even three-dimensional heat conduction problems to assess the thermal spiking behavior of these structures during processing.

2.2 Consolidation Effects

Most advanced composites applications are currently manufactured by lamination of prepreg plies. To consolidate the structure and increase the fiber volume fraction, these prepreg plies are usually bled during processing in an effort to remove excess resin. Bleeder plies are

used to soak up the resin and the thickness of the part decreases as resin is removed. Thick composites are difficult to consolidate because the outer skins usually cure first.

When a polymer cures, the viscosity increases rapidly as the crosslink density increases. When viscosity increases it becomes more difficult to extract the excess resin from the laminate. Eventually, the viscosity is too high for the polymer to flow. The inherently poor thermal conduction through the thickness of polymer composites leads to a non-uniform cure distribution. As the outer edges heat up and thermal energy slowly diffuses into the interior region, the viscosity of the outer edges is sufficiently low to remove excess resin in the outer skins. Eventually, the degree of cure in the outer regions approaches the gel point and the viscosity there becomes quite high. The interior region may still be uncured with an excess amount of resin. However, the cured outer skin effectively seals the interior region from further resin flow. The excess resin is trapped in the interior and a non-uniform fiber volume distribution across the thickness is the result.

In consolidation there is a need to define what is meant by a thick plate. Just as the Damkohler number was used in thermal analysis, another non-dimensional number, β , may be defined for consolidation effects.

$$\beta = \frac{\left(\frac{h^2 \Delta v_f \mu(T)}{S_{zz} \Delta P} \right)}{t_{gel}} \approx \frac{t_{consolidation}}{t_{gelation}} \quad (2)$$

The numerator in Equation (2) is the characteristic time for transverse compaction of a flat plate where the change in fiber volume fraction is Δv_f , the pressure differential is ΔP , the transverse permeability is S_{zz} , the viscosity is μ , and T is the isothermal cure temperature. The denominator in Equation (2) is the gelation time for a polymer matrix. Note that $(\Delta v_f / \Delta P)$ is a single material property of the composite system.

For the specific case of a polymer which obeys n^{th} order reaction kinetics, the gelation time can be approximated by

$$t_{gel} = \frac{1}{1-n} \left\{ 1 - (1 - \alpha_{gel})^{1-n} \right\} \frac{1}{A \exp\left[\frac{-\Delta E_{\alpha}}{T} \right]} \quad (3)$$

The degree of cure at gelation is α_{gel} , n is the order of the reaction, A is the frequency factor, and ΔE_{α} is the activation energy for curing. For a typical epoxy $\alpha_{gel} = 0.4 \rightarrow 0.6$.

If $\beta > 1$ in Equation (2) then the consolidation process takes longer than the gelation process and the plate can be defined as thick with respect to consolidation. When $\beta < 1$ then gelation proceeds at a sufficiently slow rate to achieve consolidation throughout the plate thickness.

3. Processing Methods

The most common method used to manufacture thick (or thin) composite structures is the autoclave method. Here the structure is fabricated by some suitable technique like lamination, filament winding, or braiding and the part is cured by subjecting it to a

temperature/vacuum/pressure history inside an autoclave. For thick structures this method of curing is plagued by the processing problems previously discussed. The manufacturer's recommended cure cycle must be altered to protect from excessive thermal spiking [11] and to achieve reasonable consolidation.

Even with cure cycle modifications, the autoclaving method is ill-suited for thick composites curing. Thermal spiking can never be suppressed entirely. And, the limits placed on the governing dimensionless parameters, $\beta < 1$ and $Da < 1$, necessitate the use of extremely long cure cycle times. This increases the cost of manufacturing.

4. Alternative Methods for the Manufacturing of Thick Composites

4.1 Staged-Curing Method

The use of staged-curing was formulated to address the problems associated with consolidation of thick composite materials. A schematic of the processing method is shown in Figure 1. A certain thickness, h_0 , is fabricated using any suitable technique (such as hand lay-up, filament winding, etc.). This "thin" structure is subjected to a Stage 1 cure cycle which achieves a uniform consolidation of the part. Stage 1 curing should induce gelation through the entire thickness, h_0 . Subsequently, another incremental thickness, h_0 , is added and the structure is again subjected to a Stage 1 cure cycle. This process is repeated until the desired thickness is achieved. Afterwards, the entire structure must be subjected to a finishing cure cycle (Stage 2).

Figure 1. The Staged Curing Method for Processing of Composite Materials

Structures fabricated using this technique can achieve uniform, high fiber volume fraction consolidations. Since each "thin" incremental stage is partially cured before the final cure cycle, a certain amount of the total exothermic energy of the material is released during

each of the Stage 1 cures. This leaves only a fraction of the original exotherm available during the final cure cycle and thermal spiking becomes less of a problem. Care must be taken to retain enough of the exotherm to achieve a strong interstage bond after the final cure. In terms of the dimensionless parameters defined previously, the consolidation of the thick structure (where $\beta > 1$) is achieved by reducing the thickness, h , in Equation 2 until $\beta < 1$. Since part of the heat of reaction is released during the Stage 1 cures, the Da number is reduced as H_R decreases. It should be noted that this processing method does not insure that $Da < 1$. Thermal spiking may still be unavoidable since a certain fraction of the original heat of reaction must be retained for the final Stage 2 cure cycle.

The author's research with this processing method has shown that uniform consolidations can be obtained while mitigating the thermal spiking problems associated with processing of thick graphite/epoxy laminates [6]. Mechanical behavior of the interstage bond as characterized by double cantilever beam mode-I fracture toughness and interlaminar shear strength showed that there was no sacrifice in mechanical performance for the processing conditions used in the study.

In addition to the obvious benefits from achieving uniform consolidation of thick composites using the staged-curing method, this processing technique is well-suited for the processing of complex structures with non-uniform cross-sectional thicknesses. For instance, a structure which varies in thickness from several hundred plies to several tens of plies is difficult to process since the requirements on the cure cycle are different for each section of the structure. The thick section requires slow heating rates and lengthy dwell times. The thin section does not and it will cure much faster through the thickness. By stage curing the thick section, the entire structure can be subjected to the final curing stage without competing requirements placed on the cure cycle. This concept has many benefits for the design of integrated structural components where the loading conditions (and structural thickness) are very different between adjacent sections of the structure.

4.2 Continuous Curing Method

Another manufacturing technique which has been developed for thick composites is called the continuous curing method. A schematic of the process is shown in Figure 2. In this case fresh (uncured) material is continuously added to the structure while simultaneously propagating a cure wave through the thickness. This cure wave can be initiated by heating the mold surface to a specified temperature. At any given time during the process, the thermal and degree of cure distributions through the thickness will look similar to that shown in Figure 2. Eventually, the desired thickness is reached and the cure front propagates to the outer edge of the structure.

The accretion of material occurs at a controllable speed, v_m . The cure front moves through the thickness at a speed, v_c . The thermal front moves through the thickness at a speed, v_t . The objective for stable curing is to match these three speeds so that $v_m = v_c = v_t$. If this condition holds true, then an infinitely thick structure could be processed by continuous curing.

To continuously cure a structure a certain initial thickness must be fabricated first. Then the mold surface temperature is raised to a specified temperature, T_0 , to initiate the crosslinking reaction. Accretion of material onto the outer surface is commenced at a controlled speed v_m . After an initial transient thermal condition, the cure front and thermal fronts propagate at a stable speed throughout the thickness. In the stable regime the cure is confined to a narrow band of material relatively close to the surface of the part. Thus, consolidation can occur in this boundary layer before full cure is

Figure 2. The Continuous Curing Method for Processing of Composite Materials: (a) Process schematic, (b) Parameter distribution through the thickness at a given time, t .

achieved. The novelty of this type of processing is that the heat of reaction is now used to drive the cure front through the material. In conventional processing the heat of reaction leads to thermal spiking and associated problems. Thus, the heat of reaction is used efficiently in continuous curing for the benefit of the processing method instead of trying to minimize its effect by partially pre-curing or using extremely slow heatup rates.

Several analytical treatments have been applied to the modeling of continuous curing [2,3,12]. The effect of activation energy and frequency factor on cure front propagation speeds

can be found in [3]. The finite difference method is used to analyze the continuous curing of AS4/3501-6 thick plates in [2]. An asymptotic analysis for large activation energy materials is presented in [12]. Demonstration pieces were processed using this method in [2]. Mechanical testing of a four inch thick AS4/3501-6 plate manufactured by continuous curing is currently being completed.

Not only is the continuous curing method inherently suited for processing of thick composites, but the concepts can be applied to thin structures as well. The benefit over conventional processing here is that there is no need to laminate or wind the structure in a separate process. The fabrication and curing processes are integrated realizing a significant savings in overall manufacturing cycle times.

5. Conclusions

Thick composite materials are difficult to process due to thermal spiking and incomplete consolidation. It is important to obtain a proper definition of what is regarded as a thick structure. What may be regarded as thick for consolidation purposes may not be when considering thermal spiking or vice versa.

A thermally-thick composite may be defined by using the Damkohler number in Equation (1). For cases where the $Da > 1$, thermal spiking is possible. Equation (1) provides a framework with which the material properties and structural geometry may be varied to achieve $Da < 1$.

A thick composite from a consolidation standpoint can be defined using Equation (2). If $\beta > 1$ then incomplete consolidation is a possibility. Again, the definition in Equation (2) provides a framework with which the material properties and structural geometry may be varied to achieve $\beta < 1$.

Two processing methods have been developed for thick composites processing. The stage-curing method achieves a uniform consolidation by incrementally subjecting the structure to several consolidation steps. The thermal spiking effect is mitigated by releasing a fraction of the original heat of reaction before the final cure cycle. Continuous curing is an inherently stable curing method where material is continuously added to the outer edge of a structure and a cure front is propagated through the thickness. Consolidation occurs in a relatively thin boundary region near the outer surface. The heat of reaction is used to drive the cure front through the material thickness so that the material is essentially self-curing. By controlling the material accretion rate, thermal spiking is non-existent.

6. References

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